

DELIVERABLE

D. 2.1.1 LIST OF THE RELEVANT INDICATORS FOR THE ASSESSMENT OF THE WELFARE OF BROILERS ON FARM

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1. Introduction

1.1. Activity 2. Animal welfare indicators, methods for the assessment and methods of improvement

Article 21 (8) (e) of Regulation **(EU) 2017/625** states that “the Commission shall lay down rules on the cases and conditions where official controls to verify compliance with animal welfare requirements may include the use of specific animal welfare indicators based on measurable performance criteria, and the design of such indicators on the basis of scientific and technical evidence”. The European Union Reference Centre for animal welfare for poultry and other small farmed animals should provide scientific and technological expertise for the development and application of the animal welfare indicators referred to in point (e) of **Article 21(8)** and **Article 96 (b)** and developing or coordinating the development of methods for the assessments of the level of welfare of animals and of methods for the improvement of the welfare of animals (**Article 96 (c)**).

1.2. Sub-activity 2.1: Relevant animal welfare indicators

The set of deliverable is part of the sub-activity 2.1 “relevant animal welfare indicators”, which aims to list the poultry welfare indicators regarding the three priority area:

Priority 1. Broilers welfare on farm.

Priority 2. Laying hens welfare in alternative housing systems.

Priority 3. State of consciousness after waterbath stunning of broilers and turkeys.

*This deliverable focuses only on: **Priority 1.** Broilers welfare on farm.*

The set of deliverable (one per priority area) will be followed up with future output of the same sub-activity, such as the description of the considered validated indicators among the identified ones and associated methodology and the identification of gaps of knowledge regarding missing/not validated indicators and prioritisation of the future topics to work on during the next period. This deliverable is also the base for sub-activity 2.2 to identify the legal requirements which are more difficult to implement and to propose better indicators and methods of animal welfare assessment. Furthermore, it will help in sub-activity 3.1 to identify the gaps of knowledge regarding indicators to check legal requirements and formulate different topics for scientific and technical studies.

This set of deliverable identifies the legal requirements of the legislation and addresses their corresponding specific indicators for each requirement, classified as animal-based, resource-based and management-based indicators. The indicators have been retrieved from literature review and expert knowledge. Furthermore, the legal requirements without specific corresponding indicators have been identified. The search of missing specific indicators in national guidance and the assessment of validity of the key indicators identified here will be reviewed in the next deliverables (deliverables **D.2.1.2** and **D.2.1.3**). Furthermore, a description of improved methods for the assessment of welfare will be provided (deliverable

D.2.2.2). This document is only delivering the indicators that can be directly linked with a specific legal requirement. Broader indicators on animal welfare for each priority area will be delivered in the next working period under the denomination “iceberg indicators”.

Definition and examples of the terminology used:

Legal requirement: a requisite of the EU legislation to be assessed during the official controls.

Example: Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 10: *“Temperature, relative air humidity [...] must be kept within limits which are not harmful to the animals”*.

Indicator: an occurrence, observation, record or measurement which has a proven relationship with the legal requirement, which can be:

- **Animal-based indicator (ABI):** a response of an animal or an effect on an animal used to assess its welfare. It can be taken directly on the animal or indirectly and includes the use of animal records.

Example: huddling as ABI of cold stress and panting as ABI of heat stress.

- **Resource-based indicator (RBI):** an evaluation of a feature of the environment in which the animal is kept or to which it is exposed.

Example: Environmental temperature, humidity.

- **Management-based indicator (MBI):** an evaluation of what the animal unit manager or stockperson does, and which management processes or tools are used.

Example: Protocol for activation of the ventilation system.

Method for the assessment: a form of evaluation of the indicators to be used in the verification of compliance with legislation.

Example: Examine groups of birds at up to 5 well-distributed locations. If birds are panting, count out 100 birds (do not disturb them and leave them sitting where they are) and estimate how many of the 100 birds are panting.

Area of concern: the difficulties of an indicator to be used or implemented.

Example: problem with validity, repeatability or feasibility.

Gap of knowledge: lack of technical and scientific information about the indicators.

Example: The large differences of THI values obtained from different equations evidence the limitations of using THI as the unique indicator of thermal stress. Moreover, THI does not take into account the ventilation level, the genotype, age or stocking density.

3. List of relevant welfare indicators of broiler welfare on farm

3.1. Legal requirement: *“Animals shall be cared for by a sufficient number of staff”* (Directive 98/58/EC, Annex, Paragraph 1).

3.1.1. ABI: None.

3.1.2. RBI:

- Number of employees in relation to farming area (m²) and/or in relation to number of animals.

Gap of knowledge: Difficult to define since “sufficient number” is related to many factors such as farm layout, technology and staff quality etc.

3.1.3. MBI: None.

3.2. Legal requirement: *“The keeper of the chickens shall hold a certificate which is recognised by the competent authority of the Member State concerned, attesting to the completion of such a training course or to having acquired experience equivalent to such training”* (Directive 2007/43 EC, Article 4).

3.2.1. ABI: None.

3.2.2. RBI: None.

3.2.3. MBI:

- Evidence of the certificate (including equivalence certificates).

3.3. Legal requirement: *“The owner or keeper shall provide instructions and guidance on the relevant animal welfare requirements, including those concerning the methods of culling practised in holdings, to persons employed or engaged by them to attend to chickens or to catch and load them”* (Directive 2007/43 EC, Article 4).

3.3.1. ABI: None.

3.3.2. RBI : None.

3.3.3. MBI :

- Written instructions and guidance provided to and signed by staff as proof of evidence.

3.4. Legal requirement: *“All chickens kept on the holding must be inspected at least twice a day. Special attention should be paid to signs indicating a reduced level of animal welfare and/or animal health”* (Directive 2007/43 EC, Annex 1, Paragraph 8).

3.4.1. ABI: None.

3.4.2. RBI: None.

3.4.3. MBI:

- Records of frequency of inspections/ keeper's feedback on inspections.
- Criteria (e.g., dead animals, lame animals...) of inspection.

Gap of knowledge: list of indicators (“*indicating a reduced level of animal welfare and/or animal health*”) the farmer should look at and methods of assessment (e.g., transect walk assessment).

3.5. Legal requirement: “*Chickens that are seriously injured or show evident signs of health disorder, such as those having difficulties in walking, severe ascites or severe malformations, and are likely to suffer, shall receive appropriate treatment or be culled immediately*” (Directive 2007/43 EC, Annex I, Paragraph 9).

3.5.1. ABI:

On-farm:

- Lameness.
- Hock burn.
- Footpad dermatitis (FPD).
- Breast blisters.
- Dead animals.

Flock register consultation to examine:

- Veterinary treatments.
- Medical interventions.
- Weight gain.
- Mortality.

At slaughter:

- Undersized animals.

3.5.2. RBI: None.

3.5.3. MBI:

- Culling rate.
- Presence of a standard operating procedures (SOPs) for identifying and treating suffering animals and conformity of the culling methods with Reg. 1099/2009.

3.6. Legal requirement: “*A veterinarian shall be contacted whenever necessary*” (Directive 2007/43 EC, Annex I, Paragraph 9).

3.6.1. ABI:

- Inspection of animals (flock health issues with no evidence of veterinarian consultation/intervention, *i.e.* sudden rises in mortality, respiratory syndromes, intestinal disorders etc.).

3.6.2. RBI: None.

3.6.3. MBI:

- Inspection of records (flock health issues with no evidence of veterinarian consultation/intervention, *i.e.* sudden rises in mortality, respiratory syndromes, intestinal disorders etc.).
- Register consultation: check veterinary visits and prescriptions.

3.7. Legal requirement: *“Animals must be fed a wholesome diet which is appropriate to their age and species and which is fed to them in sufficient quantity to maintain them in good health and satisfy their nutritional needs”* (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 14).

3.7.1. ABI:

On farm:

- Flock weight uniformity.
- Growth rate (according to genetic providers’ manuals).
- Walking ability.
- Feather integrity.
- Feather cleanliness.
- Faeces appearance.

At slaughter:

- Emaciated animals.
- Flock uniformity.

3.7.2. RBI:

- Inspection of feed labels.
- Inspection of feed program (in relation to the rearing period according to nutritional Requirement guidelines).

3.7.3. MBI: None.

3.8. Legal requirement: *“All animals must have access to feed at intervals appropriate to their physiological need”* (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 15).

3.8.1. ABI: None.

3.8.2. RBI:

- Check of the setting of the automated feed distribution system (control unit).

3.8.3. MBI:

- Flock register consultation: check farm technician's feeding instructions.
- Keeper's feedback.

3.9. Legal requirement: *“Feed shall be either continuously available or be meal fed and must not be withdrawn from chickens more than 12 hours before the expected slaughter time”* (Directive 2007/43 EC, Annex I, Paragraph 2).

3.9.1. ABI: None.

3.9.2. RBI:

- Check the settings of the automated feed distribution system (control unit).

3.9.3. MBI:

- Keeper’s feedback.
- Consultation of transport document reporting withdrawal time.

3.10. Legal requirement: *“All animals must have access to a suitable water supply or be able to satisfy their fluid intake needs by other means”* (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 16 - Directive 98/83/CE, Annex II).

3.10.1. ABI: None.

3.10.2. RBI:

- Water cleanliness.

3.10.3. MBI:

- Evidence of water quality controls.

3.11. Legal requirement: *“Drinkers shall be positioned and maintained in such a way that spillage is minimised”* (Directive 2007/43 EC, Annex I, Paragraph 1).

3.11.1. ABI:

- Animals’ drinking posture.

3.11.2. RBI:

- Check litter wetness below the drinker lines.
- Check the presence of water and the proper functioning of watering equipment (leak-free and not clogged drinkers).

3.11.3. MBI:

- Presence of SOPs regarding drinkers' management.

3.12. Legal requirement: *“All chickens shall have permanent access to litter which is dry and friable on the surface”* (Directive 2007/43 EC, Annex I, Paragraph 3).

3.12.1. ABI:

On farm:

- Feather cleanliness.
- Dust bathing behaviour (Meluzzi *et al.*, 2008).

At slaughter:

- Footpad dermatitis (Greene *et al.*, 1985; Algers *et al.*, 1989; Mayne, 2005; Allain *et al.*, 2009; Shepherd and Fairchild, 2010).
- Hock burns (de Jong *et al.* 2014).

3.12.2. RBI:

- Litter quality (Welfare Quality®, 2009; Vinco *et al.* 2018).

3.12.3. MBI: None.

3.13. Legal requirement: *“Materials to be used for the construction of accommodation, and in particular for the construction of pens and equipment with which the animals may come into contact, must not be harmful to the animals and must be capable of being thoroughly cleaned and disinfected. Accommodation and fittings for securing animals shall be constructed and maintained so that there are no sharp edges or protrusions likely to cause injury to the animals”* (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraphs 8-9).

3.13.1. ABI:

- Injuries related to the environment.

3.13.2. RBI:

- Inspection of the shed (*i.e.*, presence of sharp edges or protrusions).

3.13.3. MBI: None.

3.14. Legal requirement: *“The freedom of movement of an animal, having regard to its species and in accordance with established experience and scientific knowledge, must not be restricted in such a way as to cause it unnecessary suffering or injury”* (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 7).

Member States shall ensure that the maximum stocking density in a holding or a house of a holding does not at any time exceed 33 kg/m². When a derogation is granted under paragraph 3, the maximum stocking density in a holding or a house of a holding does not at any time exceed 39 kg/m². When the criteria set out in Annex V are fulfilled, Member States may allow that the maximum stocking density referred to in paragraph 4 be increased by a maximum of 3 kg/m² (Directive 2007/43 EC, Article 3).

3.14.1. ABI: None.

3.14.2. RBI:

- Stocking density (kg/m²).

3.14.3. MBI:

- Check for presence of documentation supporting stocking density used.

3.15. Legal requirement: *“Feeding equipment must be designed, constructed and placed so that contamination of food and the harmful effects of competition between the animals are minimised”* (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraphs 14, 15 and 17).

3.15.1. ABI:

- Back scratches due to crowding around the feeders.
- Flock uniformity.

3.15.2. RBI:

- Cm of feeder space/bird.
- Inspection of feeders (correct position and feeder and feed cleanliness).

3.15.3. MBI: None.

3.16. Legal requirement: *“Watering equipment must be designed, constructed and placed so that contamination of water and the harmful effects of competition between the animals are minimised”* (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraphs 16 and 17).

3.16.1. ABI:

- Competition between animals trying to reach the drinker.

3.16.2. RBI:

- Drinker space per bird: calculate the total number drinkers in the house according to drinker type and to the number of birds in the house (Welfare Quality®, 2009).

3.16.3. MBI:

- Presence of SOPs regarding drinkers' management.

3.17. Legal requirement: *“Where necessary sick or injured animals shall be isolated in suitable accommodation with, where appropriate, dry comfortable bedding”* (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 4).

3.17.1. ABI:

- Presence of sick or severely injured animals in the flock, neither managed nor isolated.

3.17.2. RBI:

- Presence of a suitable accommodation.

- Presence of sick or injured animals in the isolated area.

3.17.3. MBI:

- SOPs for the set up and management of the accommodation.

3.18. Legal requirement: “[...] temperature, relative air humidity [...] must be kept within limits which are not harmful to the animals” (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 10).

Ventilation shall be sufficient to avoid overheating and, where necessary, in combination with heating systems to remove excessive moisture” (Directive 2007/43 EC, Annex I, Paragraph 4).

3.18.1. ABI:

- Panting (high effective temperature).
Definition: “Breathing rapidly and in short gasps” (Welfare Quality®, 2009).
- Huddling (low effective temperature).
Definition: “Birds grouping together into tight groups, sitting closely alongside each other, often in ‘clumps’ with areas of empty space in between” (Welfare Quality®, 2009).
- Shivering (low effective temperature, extreme case).
– Definition: “Shaking slightly and uncontrollably” (Strawford *et al.*, 2011).
- Changes in the spatial distribution of birds (OIE, 2015).
- Ammonia burns on the breast.
- Footpad dermatitis (Weaver and Meijerhof, 1991).

3.18.2. RBI:

- Temperature measurements in the barn or recordings in the control panel.
- Humidity measurements in the barn or recordings in the control panel.
- Temperature Humidity Index (THI).

Area of concern: there are many different THI equations formulas to calculate the THI depending on the characteristic of the climatic conditions that animals will be submitted to.

3.18.3. MBI:

- SOPs in use for environmental control.

3.19. Legal requirement: “Requirements for the use of higher stocking densities: The owner or keeper shall ensure that each house of a holding is equipped with ventilation and, if necessary, heating and cooling systems designed, constructed and operated in such a way that: [...]; (b) the inside temperature, when the outside temperature measured in the shade exceeds 30° C, does not exceed this outside temperature by more than 3° C; (c) the average relative humidity measured inside the house during 48 hours does not exceed 70 % when the outside temperature is below 10° C” (Directive 2007/43 EC, Annex II, Paragraph 3).

3.19.1. ABI: None.

3.19.2. RBI:

- Design and functioning of ventilation, heating and cooling systems.

- Temperature and humidity recordings or temperature and humidity measurements in different spots.

3.19.3. MBI:

Statement of the environment control system supplier, that the system satisfies the requirements.

3.20. Legal requirement: “[...] gas concentrations must be kept within limits which are not harmful to the animals” (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 10).

3.20.1. ABI:

- Eye damage in the form of conjunctivitis, keratoconjunctivitis (Ritz *et al.*, 2004) or blindness (Kristensen and Wathes, 2000).
- Dyspnea (Carlile, 1984).
- Flock register consultation to check the frequency of respiratory pathologies (Ritz *et al.*, 2004).

3.20.2. RBI:

- Sensorial evaluation of ammonia concentration (eyes or nose irritation, after at least 5 minutes inside).
- Instrumental measuring of gases at broiler head height.

3.20.3. MBI: None.

3.21. Legal requirement: “Requirements for the use of higher stocking densities: The owner or keeper shall ensure that each house of a holding is equipped with ventilation and, if necessary, heating and cooling systems designed, constructed and operated in such a way that: (a) the concentration of ammonia (NH₃) does not exceed 20 ppm and the concentration of carbon dioxide (CO₂) does not exceed 3000 ppm measured at the level of the chickens’ heads” (Directive 2007/43 EC, Annex II, Paragraph 3).

3.21.1. ABI:

- Ocular abnormalities (signs of eye irritation).
- Keratitis (Miles *et al.*, 2006).

3.21.2. RBI:

- Gas concentrations measured at broiler head height with a measure tool.

3.21.3. MBI:

Description in SOPs of design, construction and operation of the ventilation and where necessary heating and cooling systems, for ensuring to meet the environmental parameters requested.

3.22. Legal requirement: “[...] dust levels must be kept within limits which are not harmful to the animals” (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 10).

3.22.1. ABI:

- Flock register consultation to check the frequency of respiratory pathologies (Al Homidan *et al.*, 2003).

3.22.2. RBI:

- Visual inspection and sensorial evaluation (stinging, irritation, visibility...) of dust level.
- Dust sheet test (Welfare Quality®, 2009).

3.22.3. MBI: None.

3.23. Legal requirement: “All buildings shall have lighting with an intensity of at least 20 lux during the lighting periods, measured at bird eye level and illuminating at least 80% of the usable area. A temporary reduction in the lighting level may be allowed when necessary following veterinary advice” (Directive 2007/43 EU, Annex I, Paragraph 6).

3.23.1. ABI:

At slaughter:

- Abnormal size of the eyes (Blatchford *et al.*, 2009; Deep *et al.*, 2010).

3.23.2. RBI:

- Light intensity (inspectors read a document out at arms' length, at bird eye level in several areas).

Area of concern: different visual capacity of assessors

- Instrumental evaluation by use of a lux meter in case of doubt.

3.23.3. MBI: None.

3.24. Legal requirement: “Animals kept in buildings must not be kept either in permanent darkness or without an appropriate period of rest from artificial lighting. Within seven days from the time when the chickens are placed in the building and until three days before the foreseen time of slaughter, the lighting must follow a 24-hour rhythm and include periods of darkness lasting at least six hours in total, with at least one uninterrupted period of darkness of at least four hours, excluding dimming periods” (Directive 98/58 EU, Annex, Paragraph 11 - Directive 2007/43 EU, Annex I, Paragraph 7).

3.24.1. ABI : None.

3.24.2. RBI: None.

3.24.3. MBI:

- Inspection of records/central unit when light program is automated.
- Farmer's feedback.

3.25. Legal requirement: *"The sound level shall be minimised. Ventilation fans, feeding machinery or other equipment shall be constructed, placed, operated and maintained in such a way that they cause the least possible amount of noise"* (Directive 2007/43 EU, Annex I, Paragraph 5).

3.25.1. ABI:

- Panic reactions after a loud sudden noise (e.g., piling up in the corners).
- Smothering.

3.25.2. RBI:

- Instrumental evaluation of sound level.

3.25.3. MBI: None.

3.26. Legal requirement: *"All surgical interventions carried out for reasons other than therapeutic or diagnostic purposes which result in damage to or the loss of a sensitive part of the body or the alteration of bone structure shall be prohibited"* (Directive 2007/43 EU, Annex I, Paragraph 12).

3.26.1. ABI:

- Animals with prohibited mutilations.

3.26.2. RBI: None.

3.26.3. MBI: None.

3.27. Legal requirement: *"Beak trimming may be authorised by Member States when other measures to prevent feather pecking and cannibalism are exhausted. In addition, Member States may authorise the castration of chickens"* (Directive 2007/43 EU, Annex I, Paragraph 12).

3.27.1. ABI: None.

3.27.2. RBI: None.

3.27.3. MBI: None.

3.28. Legal requirement: *"In such cases, if [beak trimming] shall be carried out only after consultation and on the advice of a veterinarian and shall be carried out by qualified staff on chickens that are less than 10 days*

old. [...] The castration shall only be carried out under veterinary supervision by personnel who have received a specific training” (Directive 2007/43 EU, Annex I, Paragraph 12).

3.28.1. ABI:

- Beak trimming quality (length of the portion of beak trimmed, neuromas).
- Mortality (related to castration since when castration is performed there may be an increase in mortality in relation to the quality of the intervention).

3.28.2. RBI:

- Inspection of veterinarian attestation about castration.
- Inspection of a documentary proof of a castration training course.

3.28.3. MBI:

- Keeper’s feedback.

3.29. Legal requirement: “Adequate lighting (fixed or portable) shall be available to enable the animals to be thoroughly inspected at any time” (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 3).

3.29.1. ABI: None.

3.29.2. RBI:

- Possibility to see the animals.
- Presence of specific devices.

3.29.3. MBI: None.

3.30. Legal requirement: “All automated or mechanical equipment essential for the health and well-being of the animals must be inspected at least once daily” (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 13).

3.30.1. ABI: None.

3.30.2. RBI:

- Visual control of proper functioning of feeders, drinkers, ventilation and alarm system.

3.30.3. MBI:

- Documentary inspection of records (some farmers write a short comment after every inspection of equipment as they are required by their own guides to good management practice).
- Keeper’s feedback.

3.31. Legal requirement: *“Where defects are discovered, these must be rectified immediately, or if this is impossible, appropriate steps must be taken to safeguard the health and well-being of the animals”* (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 13).

3.31.1. ABI : None.

3.31.2. RBI : None.

3.31.3. MBI :

- Evidence of maintenance intervention.
- Presence of SOPs regarding management of emergency situations.

3.32. Legal requirement: *“In the event of failure of the [ventilation] system an alarm system must be provided to give warning of breakdown. The alarm system must be tested regularly”* (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 13).

3.32.1. ABI: None.

3.32.2. RBI:

- Visual inspection of proper functioning of the alarm system.
- Documentary inspection of records of regular testing of the alarm system.

3.32.3. MBI: None.

3.33. Legal requirement: *“Where the health and well-being of the animals is dependent on an artificial ventilation system, provision must be made for an appropriate backup system to guarantee sufficient air renewal to preserve the health and well-being of the animals”* (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 13).

3.33.1. ABI: None.

3.33.2. RBI:

- Inspection of presence and adequacy of backup system.

3.33.3. MBI: None.

3.34. Legal requirement: *“The owner or keeper of the animals shall maintain a record of any medical treatment given and of the number of mortalities found to each inspection. The register of the medical treatments must be retained for a period of at least five years”* (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 5).

3.34.1. ABI: None.

3.34.2. RBI:

- Documentary inspection.

3.34.3. MBI: None.

3.35. Legal requirement: *“The owner or keeper shall maintain a record for each house of a holding of: (a) the number of chickens introduced; (b) the useable area; (c) the hybrid or breed of the chickens, if known; (d) by each control, the number of birds found dead with an indication of the causes, if known as well as the number of birds culled with cause; (e) the number of chickens remaining in the flock following the removal of chickens for sale or for slaughter”* (Directive 2007/43 EC, Annex I, Paragraph 11).

3.35.1. ABI: None.

3.35.2. RBI:

- Documentary inspection.

3.35.3. MBI: None.

3.36. Legal requirement: *“Those records [Directive 2007/43 EC, Annex I, Paragraph 11] shall be retained for a period of at least three years and shall be made available to the competent authority when carrying out an inspection or when otherwise requested”* (Directive 2007/43 EC, Annex I, Paragraph 11).

3.36.1. ABI: None.

3.36.2. RBI:

- Documentary inspection.

3.36.3. MBI: None.

3.37. Legal requirement: *“Member States shall encourage the development of guides to good management practice which shall include guidance on compliance with this Directive. The dissemination and use of such guides shall be encouraged”* (Directive 2007/43 EC, Article 8).

3.37.1. ABI: None.

3.37.2. RBI:

- Documentary inspection.

3.37.3. MBI: None.

3.38. Legal requirement: *“No other substance, with the exception of those given for therapeutic, or prophylactic purposes or for the purposes of zootechnical treatment as defined in Article 1(2)(c) of Directive 96/22/EEC (1), must be administered to an animal unless it has been demonstrated by scientific studies of animal welfare or established experience that the effect of that substance is not detrimental to the health or welfare of the animal”* (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 18).

3.38.1. ABI: None.

3.38.2. RBI:

- Documentary inspection: check veterinary prescription in the flock register and for other products (with no veterinary prescription) check packaging and package leaflet.

3.38.3. MBI:

- Reports of self and official controls (sampling birds, water, feed, and environment).

3.39. Legal requirement: *“Requirements for the use of higher stocking densities (>33 kg/m²): The owner or keeper shall maintain and have available in the house compiled documentation describing in detail the production systems. In particular it shall include information on technical details of the house and its equipment such as: (a) a plan of the house including the dimensions of the surfaces occupied by the chickens; (b) ventilation and, if relevant, cooling and heating system, including their location, a ventilation plan, detailing target air quality parameters, such as airflow, air speed and temperature; (c) feeding and watering systems and their location; (d) alarm systems and backup systems in the event of a failure of any automated or mechanical equipment essential for the health and well-being of the animals; (e) floor type and litter normally used”* (Directive 2007/43 EC, Annex II, Paragraph 2).

3.39.1. ABI: None.

3.39.2. RBI: None.

3.39.3. MBI:

- Documentary inspection of the written procedure.

3.40. Legal requirement: *“Criteria for the use of increased stocking density (up to 42 kg/m²): Criteria: (a) the monitoring of the holding carried out by the competent authority within the last two years did not reveal any deficiencies with respect to the requirements of this Directive, and (b) the monitoring by the owner or keeper of the holding is carried out using the guides to good management practice referred to in Article 8, and (c) in at least seven consecutive, subsequently checked flocks from a house the cumulative daily mortality rate was below 1 % + 0,06 % multiplied by the slaughter age of the flock in days”* (Directive 2007/43 EC, Annex V, Paragraph 1).

3.40.1. ABI:

- Cumulative daily mortality rate.

3.40.2. RBI:

- Documentary inspection (results of CA monitoring).

3.40.3. MBI:

- Keeper’s feedback (use of guides).

3.41. Legal requirement: *“In the case of stocking densities higher than 33 kg/m², the documentation accompanying the flock shall include the daily mortality rate and the cumulative daily mortality rate calculated by the owner or keeper and the hybrid or breed of the chickens. [...] These data as well as the number of broilers dead on arrival shall be recorded, indicating the holding and the house of the holding”* (Directive 2007/43 EC, Annex III, Paragraph 1).

3.41.1. ABI:

At slaughter:

- Daily mortality rate.
- Cumulative daily mortality rate.
- Dead on arrival.

3.41.2. RBI:

- Documentary inspection.

3.41.3. MBI: None

3.42. Legal requirement: *“In the context of the controls performed under the Regulation (EC) No 854/2004, the official veterinarian shall evaluate the results of the post-mortem inspection to identify other possible indications of poor welfare conditions such as abnormal levels of contact dermatitis, parasitism and systemic illness in the holding or the unit of the house of the holding of origin”* (Directive 2007/43 EC, Annex III, Paragraph 2).

3.42.1. ABI:

At slaughter:

- Footpad dermatitis.
- Flock weight uniformity.
- Hock burn.
- Breast burn.
- Breast blisters.
- Emaciation.
- Ascites.
- Cellulitis.
- Joint lesions.
- Scratches.
- Wing fractures.

3.42.2. RBI: None.

3.42.3. MBI: None.

4. Conclusions

Conclusions specific to Priority 1 - Broilers welfare on farm:

- 1) A total of 42 legal requirements have been identified for official control, approximately half of them concerning Directive 98/58 EC and the other half Directive 2007/43 EC, with some overlapping.
- 2) Although Directive 2007/43 EC is more focused on the use of ABIs to assess animal welfare, in respect to Directive 98/58, the evaluation of the majority of the legal requirements identified in both directives cannot rely now on the use of ABIs (e.g. “sufficient number of staff”, “holding of a certificate of competence”, “number of daily inspections”).
- 3) Hence, from the total of 42 legal requirements, only 20 can be assessed using ABIs.
- 4) However, many of these ABIs are not linked to only one single legal requirement (e.g., mortality, footpad dermatitis), although precious for an overall judgment of the welfare status and the management of the animals on farm.

5. References

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